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VIEWS ON EXISTENCE AND THE STATE IN ANCIENT WESTERN PHILOSOPHY

Ergashev Ozodbek Shavkatovich

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philosophical Sciences

Andijan State Technical Institute

Department of Languages and Humanities

Annotation. The article analyzes the formation process of ancient Western philosophy, its main stages, and the philosophical views of ancient Greek thinkers on existence, change, state, and society. In particular, the teachings of Heraclitus on change and dialectics, the atomistic theory of Democritus, Plato's concept of the world of ideas and the ideal state, and Aristotle's views on being, logic and state governance are highlighted. The influence of ancient philosophy on the development of Western intellectual thought and subsequent philosophical schools is also substantiated.

Keywords: ancient philosophy, existence, state, atomism, ideal state, dialectics, ancient Greek philosophy, logic, society, philosophical thinking.

Introduction. Western philosophy began to take shape in the 7th–6th centuries BC within the ancient Greek polis. This period was an important turning point in the history of human intellectual development, initiating the process of transitioning from mythological and religious ideas to rational, logical, and theoretical thinking in human thought. Ancient Greek thinkers began to seek answers to questions about the universe, nature, man, and society not through myths and legends, but through mental observation and logical analysis.

The development of socio-political life in the Greek polis, the expansion of trade, and the strengthening of cultural ties created favorable conditions for the formation of philosophical thinking. In this environment, human knowledge of existence deepened, and the desire to explain natural phenomena through natural causes intensified. As a result, the issues of space, matter, motion, change, and cognition became the central theme of early philosophical research.

In this sense, ancient Western philosophy was of particular importance not only as an intellectual product of ancient Greek civilization but also as a solid theoretical foundation for the development of subsequent Western philosophy, science, and culture.

Body. Heraclitus was a major representative of ancient philosophy who emphasized that fire is the foundation of existence. In his teachings, fire is interpreted not only as a natural element but also as a symbol of constant movement, change, and renewal. According to Heraclitus, everything in the world is in a certain process, and nothing remains unchanged. Therefore, he put forward the famous idea that

"everything is in the flow" (Panta rhei). This idea implies that existence is dynamic rather than static.

According to Heraclitus, the world exists in a state of constant movement and change, and the primary source of development is the struggle of opposites. He emphasized that all processes in life occur through the unity and struggle of contradictions. For example, such opposite states as day and night, life and death, heat and cold cannot exist without each other, and it is their interaction that ensures progress. Heraclitus explained this process as a universal law of the universe.

Thus, Heraclitus' ideas on movement, change, and dialectics subsequently exerted a great influence on the formation of dialectical thought in the history of philosophy. His teachings served as an important theoretical source for modern philosophical views based on the understanding of existence in motion and development.

Democritus explained that the universe consists of tiny, indivisible particles—atoms. According to him, everything in the universe consists of atoms and voids, and various bodies and phenomena differ according to the shape, order, and motion of atoms. Democritus considered atoms to be eternal, immutable, and indivisible. His atomistic doctrine is significant for its focus on explaining natural phenomena based on natural causes rather than through mythological or divine forces. This theory subsequently exerted a great influence on the development of physics, chemistry, and other natural sciences, serving as an important foundation for the formation of scientific views on the structure of matter.

Plato, as a major representative of the idealistic movement in ancient philosophy, created the famous doctrine of two worlds—the world of ideas and the world of things. According to him, real existence belongs to the world of eternal and perfect ideas, and the material things observed in human sensory experience are imperfect reflections of these ideas. Therefore, true knowledge is obtained not through sensory experience, but through reason and reflection.

In Plato's Republic, the theory of the ideal state was developed. It emphasizes that society must be organized based on the principle of justice. According to Plato, the state should be governed by the wisest and most knowledgeable people—philosophers—because they can deeply understand the essence of truth and justice. He divided society into classes, such as philosophers, soldiers, and manufacturers, and showed that the basis of an ideal state is for each class to perform its duties fairly. These views of Plato had a great influence on the development of political philosophy and the theory of the state.

Aristotle is the greatest representative of ancient Western philosophy, having made a significant contribution to the development of philosophy, logic, ethics, politics, and the natural sciences. He evaluated the state as an important social institution that ensures a happy and prosperous life for a person. According to Aristotle, man is a "political being" and cannot fully develop outside of society. Therefore, the primary task of the state is to ensure the well-being, just life, and

spiritual perfection of its citizens. He analyzed various forms of government and considered the forms of government that serve the common good to be the most optimal.

One of Aristotle's most significant theoretical achievements in philosophy is the doctrine of the four causes. According to him, to fully understand any thing or phenomenon, it is necessary to know its four main reasons:

Physical cause - means what substance an object is made of;

Formal cause — expresses the structure, form, and essence of an object;

Moving cause - indicates the factor that created or moved the object;

Purposeful reason - refers to why something exists and its ultimate purpose.

This doctrine allows for a comprehensive analysis of being not only through its external appearance but also through its internal essence, origin, and purpose. Therefore, Aristotle's theory of the four causes plays an important role in the development of philosophical methodology, ontology, and the theory of scientific knowledge. His philosophical legacy exerted a profound influence on the formation of subsequent Western philosophy, particularly medieval scholasticism and modern scientific methodology.

Conclusion. Ancient Western philosophy served as a solid theoretical foundation for all subsequent philosophical schools. The ideas of being, cognition, action, logic, state, and society developed by ancient Greek thinkers were of great importance not only for their time but also for the intellectual development of subsequent centuries. Ancient philosophy initiated the process of transitioning from mythological thinking to rational and scientific observation, making a significant contribution to the formation of a culture of theoretical thinking in Western civilization.

Heraclitus' views on motion and dialectics, Democritus' atomistic theory, Plato's doctrine of the ideal state and the world of ideas, and Aristotle's ideas on logic, ontology, and politics profoundly influenced the development of later philosophical schools. Their legacy served as an important source in the formation of medieval scholasticism, modern rationalism, and modern philosophical concepts.

These philosophical views on being, movement, and the state remain relevant today. In modern philosophical research, the heritage of ancient philosophy is widely used within the framework of ontology, social philosophy, political theory, and methodology of knowledge. In this sense, ancient Western philosophy is of particular importance not only as a historical heritage but also as an important intellectual source that enriches modern scientific and philosophical research.

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